

Dali Doborjginidze**Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University (Georgia)****[dali.doborjginidze@bsu.edu.ge], ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4122-4858****Lela Tavdgiridze****Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University (Georgia)****[lela.tavdgiridze@bsu.edu.ge], ORCID ID: 0000-0001-8108-8718****Anastasia Makharadze****Faculty of Humanities & Social Sciences, Sheridan College (Canada)****[anastasia.mkhr43@gmail.com], ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6452-4044**

Innovations in Language: Principles of Teaching and Translation

Abstract: *The progress of Georgia as a sovereign state is closely linked to the European education system. The intercultural exchange of knowledge and educational ideas, facilitated by translation, is an important pillar of Georgia's integration with the European education system. The accession of the Georgian educational system to the Bologna process, the irreversible aspiration of the Georgian nation towards Europe, should be accompanied by the creation of an advanced European education system in the country, and be based on the analysis and consideration of past experiences, where the formation of a national school, which represents one of the core foundations of the state's national ideology, should naturally contribute to it.*

Translation is vital in fostering a connection between diverse educational traditions and methodologies by translating and adapting educational materials and practices from European systems to align with Georgia's cultural and linguistic context. Teaching methodology is constantly evolving and enhancing teaching effectiveness and student engagement. With modern technologies now an integral part of the younger generation's daily lives, many students expect these tools to be incorporated into their learning experience. As a result, traditional lessons can sometimes seem boring leading to a significant decline in their motivation to learn.

In this study, we employed both quantitative and qualitative research methods. Our approach included analyzing the syllabi of educational programs and reviewing relevant literature. Additionally, we designed a comprehensive questionnaire and conducted interviews with students from diverse specialties, as well as lecturers and teachers from various training centers.

The article discusses resources, strategies, approaches, practical activities, advice, experiences, and research findings on how we can best prepare our future generation for the new world that systems are moving towards. The article will also

present modern methods and principles used to translate linguistic innovations, focusing on neologisms, technical terms, slang, and linguo-culturology.

Keywords: *European Integration; Intercultural Translation; Teaching Methodology; Educational Innovation; Research Methods; Linguistic Adaptation.*

Introduction

The field of education and related issues have always been important and relevant for humanity, as it is the field on which the continuous development of any field and society is based. Education is a prerequisite for a decent life and ensuring social sustainability. Providing education is one thing, but it is more important to know how high-quality is the education we provide and, accordingly, what results we achieve.

The advancement of Georgia as an independent state is closely related to the European education system. The accession of the Georgian educational system to the Bologna Process, the irreversible aspiration of the Georgian nation towards Europe, should be accompanied by the creation of a highly developed European education system in the country, which should be based on the analysis and consideration of past experiences, where the formation of a national school, which represents one of the solid and fundamental foundations of the national ideology of the state, should naturally contribute. Indeed, the teaching methodology determines whether a learner will love the course. It also determines how consciously and thoughtfully the learner will be able to perceive, understand, and apply the material in practice. One of the most important challenges of the teaching process is to stimulate the desire to learn in students. "The development of technologies, globalization and a rapidly changing environment have created a need for education systems and goals to be in line with modern challenges. Therefore, educational institutions must ensure the preparation of educational programs that will help the next generation to be competitive, have the appropriate knowledge, skills, worldview and readiness to independently ensure the creation of decent living conditions, while at the same time being personally developed." (Tavdgiridze, and al., 2019:3).

Teaching methodology is constantly evolving and ensuring teaching effectiveness and engagement. Since modern technologies have become an integral part of the lives of the younger generation, many of them expect to use them in the learning process, so sometimes traditional lessons seem boring, which significantly reduces their motivation to learn.

One of the main goals of education is to develop independent learning skills in students. For representatives of the education sector, one of the most important questions to consider is: what skills should we equip them with so that they can effectively adapt to the modern, competitive environment? (Moir, 2022:16).

Innovations in teaching methodology have emerged as a result of the development of modern technologies, psychology, and education and serve to make the teaching process more effective, flexible, and inclusive. Accordingly, we are trying to actively introduce innovations, innovative teaching methods and approaches into the modern learning process. Along with the development of modern culture and technology, people are more often using language experiments, slang, and Internet language, which often goes beyond the norms.

Language freedom often clashes with linguistic norms. In today's dynamic world, new words, terms, and expressions are rapidly emerging in language. Translating these innovations poses a great challenge to linguists and translators, requiring a deep knowledge of the cultural context, creativity, and the ability to adapt.

The use of translation innovations in learning plays an important role in the development of students' linguistic and intercultural competence. These innovations not only facilitate language learning, but also improve the ability to understand and interpret texts.

Translation innovations in learning help students create effective and engaging learning processes. However, it is important that they use these tools as aids and not as a way to achieve the final result. The right methodology and critical thinking ensure the maximum benefit of innovations.

Translation of linguistic innovations is a dynamic and evolving field that requires creativity, cultural sensitivity, and technological support. Using a variety of methods and following guiding principles, translators fill linguistic gaps and contribute to global understanding. As language evolves, the collaboration of human expertise and technological advancement will play an important role in solving the challenges of translating new words and expressions using correct and valid methods and approaches.

Language norms, freedom, and innovation contribute to the preservation and development of the language. Modern teaching and translation methods ensure the popularization of the language and the simplification of its study. The main challenge is that changes in the language should not contradict its purity and identity.

Research methodology – This study employed both quantitative and qualitative research methods. We studied the syllabi of the following educational programs: translation studies, intercultural communication, and teacher training; relevant literature was studied and translated, in particular, the BSU team (including the co-authors of this article) translated the following books within the framework of the Higher Education Support Program:

1.11.2020-31.12.2021 Grant project within the framework of the “Higher Education Support” sub-program of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports of Adjara: Cathy Nutbrown, Peter Clough, scientific / textbook translation of “Early Childhood Education: History, Philosophy and Experience” from English to Georgian. Project Organizer. Agreement №02-10/III 4.11.2020;

2. 2020-31.12.2021 Grant project within the framework of the “Higher Education Support” sub-program of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports of Adjara: Cathy Nutbrown, Peter Clough, scientific / textbook translation of “Early Childhood Education: History, Philosophy and Experience” from English to Georgian. Project Organizer. Agreement №02-10/III 4.11.2020;

3.12.07.2022-30.07.2023- Grant project within the framework of the “Higher Education Support” sub-program of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports of Adjara: Jan White „Playing and Learning Outdoors. The Practical Guide and Sourcebook for excellence in outdoor provision and practice with young children, Third Edition (2019) from English to Georgian. Project Organizer. Agreement №04-05/185;

4.18.08.203-31.12.2024 Grant project within the framework of the “Higher Education Support” sub-program of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports of Adjara Taryn Moir " How to Create Autonomous Learners: Teaching Metacognitive, Self-regulatory and Study Skills – A Practitioner’s Guide „from English to Georgian. Project Organizer. Agreement №04-07/164 18.08.203

To achieve the set goal, we developed and conducted questionnaires and interviews with students of various disciplines, academic faculty implementing educational programs, and teachers from various training centers.

When interviewing teachers, we asked the following questions: What impact do innovative approaches to language teaching have on the quality of teaching? Do teachers use modern technologies in language teaching and translation? What difficulties do they face in translation? Which language teaching methods do they consider effective?

Do linguistic innovations reflect social and cultural changes? Since in modern society language is no longer considered a static and permanent structure – it is a living and dynamic process, which is constantly undergoing changes under the influence of technological, cultural and social factors. Linguistic innovations are especially noticeable – new vocabulary, semantic changes, slang, forms arising from foreign influence, etc. In the linguistic situation, these changes are manifested not only in everyday communication, but also affect language teaching and translation practice.

For example: post – the publication, chat –online conversation, App – mobile application, update – refresh, renew, game, screenshot – the image of a screen.

There are various reasons for language change. In this article, we will highlight some of the main ones:

Multicultural influence: the connection of different languages.

Technology and social media: the need for fast and easy communication.

Language interference: the mixing of structures by a bilingual society.

Linguistic economy: the desire to simplify speech in order to save time and energy.

These changes are natural and are part of the language evolution process. However, preserving traditional norms is important for maintaining the purity and stability of the language.

Linguistic innovations in the Georgian language in recent years, divided by sources:

Social networks and youth slang

Active linguistic innovations are developing in Georgian social networks – new words or, in the linguistics term, "hybrid constructions" are often born.

Word/phrase	Meaning	Source	Comment
Stuck	confusion, mental freeze	Facebook, Twitter	Metaphorical use (e.g. "I got stuck on the lecturer")
ფლექსაობა/Flexaoba	boasting, showing off	TikTok, YouTube	English "flex" – direct transfer, established in Georgian discourse

2. Media and Opinion journalism

Television and online media often adopt new forms based on foreign influences.

Linguistic neologisms are particularly relevant in technological and political discourse:

Word/phrase	Meaning	Source	Comment
Factchecking	Checking the facts	netgazeti.ge, mythdetector	Literal translation, firmly established term
Debate	discussion, debate	TV debates	Modified form of the English "debate"
Hater	Negative person	TV shows, blogs	Constantly used in slang style

3. Technological discourse and IT environment

With the spread of technology, professional terminology has become firmly established in the language, often in direct (non-translated) form:

Word/phrase	Meaning	Source	Comment
Default	Default setting	IT forums, support groups	Direct transliteration
Lagva (lag)	System interruption	gamer community	"Lag" – a borrowed term in Georgian grammar
Gasheareba	To share	Facebook, Messenger	"Share" + prefix "Ga" inserted in Georgian

As evidenced, in recent years terms based on foreign influences, new slang constructions and professional terminology have been actively spreading in the language, which in many cases adapt to Georgian grammatical norms. These linguistic changes are clearly fueled by social media, youth communication, technological and information space. For example, contenti – content, startupi – startup, posti – post, chati – chat, applicia – application, updaiti – update, gaimi – game, screenshoti

– screenshot, buildi – build, trendi – trend, fasheni – fashion. Identification of these trends is important for both teaching and translation fields, so that modern linguistic reality can be reflected in practice.

The language situation is considered one of the basic concepts of sociolinguistics. According to Charles **Ferguson**, the language situation refers to the overall configuration of language use at a given time and place and includes such data as how many languages there are and which languages are used in a given area, how many people use each and in what circumstances; what moods and attitudes the members of the given society have towards these languages. (Ferguson, 1971:157).

Traditional methods of language teaching often fail to reflect the rapidly evolving linguistic innovations as they develop in real discourse, which frequently results in learners and educators being insufficiently prepared to accurately perceive and analyze the nuances of contemporary discourse. This challenge is particularly significant in contexts where language teaching is accompanied by the need for translation – adequately conveying linguistic changes into another language requires not only knowledge of the language but also an understanding and interpretation of its innovative forms. This, in turn, highlights the necessity for teaching methodology to be flexible, up-to-date, and adapted to the constant transformations of linguistic reality.

This study aims to study trends related to linguistic innovations and analyze their impact on teaching methodology and translation practice. Accordingly, the student questionnaire consisted of the following questions:

What kinds of activities help you in language acquisition?

Do innovative approaches to language teaching enhance the quality of your learning?

How important are videos, audio recordings, and interactive materials to you when learning a language?

In your opinion, what role do the teacher and teaching methods play in the learning process?

What kind of feedback helps you overcome the challenges of language learning?

Do educators use modern technologies in the process of language teaching and translation process?

What would you change?

Analysis of the results of the survey conducted with teachers showed that 58% of teachers believe that innovative approaches to language teaching significantly increase the quality of teaching. 31% –

prefer traditional teaching approaches, 6% refrained from answering, 5% prefer an individual approach to teaching. The answers to the question – do teachers use modern technologies in the language teaching process? were recorded as follows: "Language is constantly changing and developing, therefore the use of modern technologies simplifies the perception of new terms and concepts.", "The use of modern technologies makes it easier for learners to perceive foreign contexts and remember words. "Working on the translation of foreign literature helps learners get closer to the cultures of different countries." "Innovations, media contribute to the improvement of learners' language competencies." "Innovations in language teaching increase learner motivation and engagement"; The following effective language teaching methods were named: playing, communicative method, team projects, simulation of real situations, games and interactive activities, language learning platforms, dialogues on real-life situations, personalized programs that make the learning process more effective. According to respondents, these methods contribute to the upbringing of creative, independent-thinking young people.

In the modern educational space, foreign language teaching is increasingly associated with innovative methods. One of the important directions is the integration of innovative approaches to translation, which helps students learn the language both at the lexical and cultural levels. Translation is no longer considered just a mechanical transfer of text from one language to another, but is an active cognitive process that contributes to the linguistic and cultural competence of the student (Cook, 2010:14-15).

How do translation innovations help students learn and make the teaching process more effective and interesting? First of all, translation innovations involve the use of modern approaches and technologies in the field of translation, for example: **multimodal translation** – incorporating video, audio, subtitles, and visual elements;

Translation applications and platforms – for example, DeepL, Google Translate or special learning apps;

Contextual translation – when words are not translated literally, but according to the context;

AI translation and real-time translation;

When asked what difficulties they encounter when translating, the majority of the students surveyed noted that language learning is directly related to translation activities. The student notes how the text

was translated taking into account the context and better understands the essence of the language, not just grammar;

How modern technologies have increased their level of inter-activity, in particular, the use of apps and platforms has allowed students to try to translate, compare, identify and correct errors on their own.

How their cultural awareness has grown – while translating, students encounter cultural differences, phraseology, and idioms, which help them not only in language, but also in perceiving the diversity of the world.

How their critical thinking developed

When a student sees how the same text can be translated in different ways, they start to think – which version is better? Why?

What also increases students' motivation? Innovative formats (e.g., video translation, game-based translation) make learning more interesting.

Modern platforms such as **DeepL**, **Google Translate**, **Mem-source**, and others are already being used in the educational process as learning resources. Students learn how to use these tools critically – comparing results, assessing translation accuracy, and mastering to access and evaluate language (Bowker & Ciro, 2019:31-33).

Translation is a complex process that requires both language knowledge and cultural competence. A literal translation, as mentioned above, often does not reflect the emotional or cultural context of the text. The translator must take into account the nuances of the language and the cultural elements that are present in the text. Often, students turn to automatic translation tools, such as Google Translate, which simplify the general translation process for them, but cannot replace human interpretation and lacks cultural competence.

Translation innovations also contribute to the development of cultural interpretation. Students acquire the ability to understand linguistic context not only at the level of words, but also at the level of culture. This process uses interactive tasks – such as translating dialogue, preparing subtitles, or localizing a poster. (Liddicoat&Scarino, 2013:45-46).

Accordingly, we actively adopt innovations in the modern educational process, introduce innovative teaching methods and diverse approaches, which reflect the challenges of global culture and the digital era (O'Hagan, 2016:88-89).

Analysis of students' responses showed that the most effective language learning approaches for them are: **Task-Based Learning**. They master the practical use of the language in real situations, such as: communication in tourist situations; professional activities, for example, business language. **Gamification (game-based learning)** – the use of games in the language learning process to increase motivation and consolidate knowledge. This includes: accumulating points, team competitions and activities. **Virtual and augmented reality (VR and AR)** – virtual environments help students practice speaking a new language, for example: virtual tours in a foreign country; dialogues in a realistic environment. **Intercultural learning – language learning – different ways of considering context**, in-depth understanding of culture and the importance of intercultural learning. International online connections (for example, PenPal programs); videos, films and audio materials that introduce us to culture. For example, one of the most common models for analyzing culture is the iceberg model. In the iceberg model, the main emphasis is placed on the constituent elements of culture, some of which are visible, while others are difficult to detect. (**Intercultural learning T-Kit**).

Developing critical thinking. Improving students' skills to enable them to deeply analyze and critically use language: discussions and debates; analysis of real-life texts (Blended learning).

In this approach, classical and online learning complement each other, providing a flexible and diverse learning experience. Flipped Classroom Models. Students prepare material in advance (for example, watching videos or reading books) and work on practical application in the classroom.

Dialogue and role-playing games, audio/video materials, independent work and projects, frequent feedback and reminder assessments, use of a variety of technologies such as applications, online courses, language learning platforms – **Duolingo, Babbel, Rosetta Stone**, intuitive applications for independent language learning, and virtual classrooms (for example, Zoom and Google Meet) for direct teacher-student interaction.

Thus, innovative approaches make the process of teaching a foreign language more flexible, effective, and diverse. They should be selected according to the needs of a specific student or group in order to make learning as effective and enjoyable/comfortable as possible.

The analysis of the syllabi showed that the following methods are used within the framework of the training course: oral methods, individualized instruction, discussion/debate; methods of working on a book/source; written methods; analysis of a case/pedagogical situation; cognitive schemes; role-playing, simulations; demonstration/presentation; project/problem-oriented learning; collaborative learning. E-learning method, micro-teaching, etc. Also, the study of teaching methods in syllabi showed that individual curriculums are developed for students with special educational needs, taking into account teaching and assessment tailored to their needs.

Language teaching has become more effective and diverse with modern methods.

Conclusions and recommendations:

The analysis of the research results showed the following: modern approaches, technologies, diverse strategies, innovations in didactics, communicative and interactive methods promote learning creativity, logical, critical thinking, and the upbringing of an independent, meta-cognitively thinking new generation; facilitate the development of linguistic communication, deepen multilingual and multicultural awareness, and bring two languages and cultures closer together, which is important for learning in a multilingual environment in the context of globalization;

Innovative approaches to translation are an important resource in the process of teaching a foreign language. They enrich the learning environment, increase students' linguistic competence, critical thinking, and cultural sensitivity. Proper methodological integration transforms this process for both the student and the teacher.

The integration of innovations in the process of teaching a foreign language changes not only the forms of teaching, but also the principles of understanding and using the language itself. Translation as a teaching method remains relevant even in an innovative environment and allows language learning to be thoughtful, in-depth, communicatively loaded and practice-oriented. Learning in the process of translation promotes in-depth understanding of the language, purposeful and creative learning; simplifies and makes language learning effective; It enlivens the language and gives it a more practical, natural, and flexible form. However, it is impossible to 'translate' the individuality of different cultures into terms that will be acceptable everywhere and to everyone. According to this view, it is impossible to evaluate cultures as 'higher' or 'more

progressive'; cultures are simply different from each other, each with its own unique and irreplaceable value.

Thus, translation, modern teaching principles and innovative approaches complement each other, together creating a powerful and result-oriented educational model that turns language learning into a deep, multifaceted and vibrant process. Maintaining a balance between norms and freedom is essential for the sustainable development of a language. Innovations and new methodologies provide new opportunities for language learning, use and translation.

Bibliography:

Bowker, L., & Buitrago-Ciro, J. (2019). *Machine Translation and Global Research: Towards Improved Machine Translation Literacy in the Scholarly Community*. Emerald Publishing.

Cook, G. (2010). *Translation in Language Teaching: An Argument for Reassessment*. Oxford University Press.

Crystal, D. (2001). *Language and the Internet*. Cambridge University Press.

Ferguson, Ch. A. (1971). *Language Structure and Language Use: Essays*. Stanford University Press, 1971:157].

Kern, R. (2000). "Literacy and Language Teaching." Oxford University Press.

Kramsch, C. (1993). "Context and Culture in Language Teaching." Oxford University Press.

Liddicoat, A. J., & Scarino, A. (2013). *Intercultural Language Teaching and Learning*. Wiley-Blackwell.

Moir, T. (2022). *Teaching Metacognitive, self-regulatory and study skills-Apprentice's Guide*, Routledge, p. 16;

O'Hagan, M. (2016). *The Routledge Handbook of Translation and Technology*. Routledge.

Tavdgiridze, L., G. Shervashidze, N. Sherozia, N. Mamuladze (2019), *Theory of Teaching and Education (Fundamentals of Didactics)*, Batumi, p. 3.

Thorne, S. L., & Reinhardt, J. (2008). "Bridging Activities, New Media Literacies, and Advanced Foreign Language Proficiency." *CALICO Journal*, 25(3), 558–572.

Widdowson, H. G. (2003). *Defining Issues in English Language Teaching*. Oxford University Press.

Intercultural learning T-Kit

<https://www.nplg.gov.ge/greenstone3/halftone-library/collection/civil2/document/HASHe955485daa78a90f78365d;jsessionid=E92A5CCE11E820685DA10890D9A3A2A4?ed=1>